

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 23rd – 29th November 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

November 18, 2020 (Evaluation & The Health Professions)

Notes from the Field: Effectiveness of Prevention and Control Measures for Imported COVID-19 in Guangming District of Shenzhen

Xiaoliang Chen, Tieqiang Wang, Yang Zhao et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0163278720971833>

The Guangming District of Shenzhen formulated a mechanism that integrated early identification, early diagnosis, early isolation, and early protection for the COVID-19 epidemic. A district-wide epidemic prevention and control system was established under the major leadership of the district government. The purpose of this paper was to describe the strategies for the control and prevention of the COVID-19 epidemic in Shenzhen Guangming District and the results of the first 50 days from January 20, as of March 13.

November 19, 2020 (PNAS)

Event-specific interventions to minimize COVID-19 transmission

Paul Tupper, Himani Boury, Madi Yerlanov, Caroline Colijn

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2019324117>

The authors provided a simple model of COVID-19 transmission at workplaces, events, and other settings. They used data from reported single-event, short-duration outbreaks to estimate the transmission rate, number of contacts, and turnover at events. Using this data, they predicted how many new infections are expected to occur at various events given the presence of a single infectious individual. They also determined which types of interventions will be the most effective in reducing the number of infections: reducing transmission rates (such as with masks), social distancing (reducing the number of people in contact), or bubbling (keeping contact groups small and consistent).

November 24, 2020 (NEJM)

A Randomized Trial of Convalescent Plasma in COVID-19 Severe Pneumonia
Simonovich V.A., Burgos Pratz L.D., Scibona P., et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2031304>

Hospitalized adults with severe COVID-19 pneumonia were randomly assigned in a 2:1 ratio to receive convalescent plasma or placebo. At 30 days, no significant difference in clinical status was noted between the two groups. Overall mortality was 11.43% with placebo and 10.96% with convalescent plasma, a difference that was not significant.

November 24, 2020 (NEJM)

A Cluster-Randomized Trial of Hydroxychloroquine for Prevention of COVID-19

Mitjà O., Corbacho-Monné M., Ubals M., et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2021801>

In a trial involving asymptomatic contacts of patients with PCR–confirmed Covid-19 in Spain, the authors compared the use of hydroxychloroquine with usual care. Postexposure therapy with hydroxychloroquine did not prevent SARS-CoV-2 infection or symptomatic Covid-19 in healthy persons.

B. Science and Engineering

November 2, 2020 (Pattern Recognition)

Automatic COVID-19 lung infected region segmentation and measurement using CT-scans images

Adel Oulefki, Sos Agaian, Thaweesak Trongtirakul et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2020.107747>

The authors designed an automatic COVID-19 Lung Infection segmentation and measurement tool using chest CT images. The extensive computer simulations show better efficiency and flexibility learning approach on CT image segmentation with image enhancement compared to the segmentation approaches. Experiments performed on COVID-CT-Dataset containing 275 CT scans that are positive and new data acquired from the EL-BAYANE center for Radiology and Medical Imaging. Their results proved that the proposed approach is more robust, accurate and straightforward.

November 4, 2020 (Biomedical Signal Processing and Control)

Control of COVID-19 system using a novel nonlinear robust control algorithm

Musadaq A. Hadi & Hazem I. Ali.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2020.102317>

In this paper, a new mathematical-engineering strategy is introduced to control the epidemic. Control theory is involved in controlling the unstable epidemic with the other suggested strategies until the vaccine is developed. A new robust control algorithm is introduced to compensate for the nonlinear system. Also, the Variable Transformation Technique is used to simplify the COVID-19 system. They claimed that the proposed control algorithm can effectively compensate the pandemic.

November 17, 2020 (Journal of Cleaner Production)

COVID-19 pandemic lessons to facilitate future engagement in the global climate crisis

Krystal M. Perkins, Nora Munguia, Michael Ellenbecker et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125178>

This article discusses six lessons drawn from the COVID-19 pandemic that can inform and facilitate greater future engagement in the global climate crisis. These lessons were identified through monitoring and analyzing media coverage of COVID-19 related events from late January 2020 to June 2020. The key lessons included the potential of reducing fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse emissions, a case for strong sustainability, a (mis)trust in science, and the possibility of a large-scale change.

November 21, 2020 (Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications)

Exact properties of SIQR model for COVID-19

Takashi Odagaki

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2020.125564>

Dr Odagaki reformulated the SIQR model where compartments for infected and quarantined are redefined to suit COVID-19 situation. He shows that the maximum number of infected depends strongly on the quarantine rate and that the quarantine measure is more effective than the lockdown measure. He then proposes a theoretical framework to find out an optimum strategy during lockdown and quarantine for minimizing the number of infection and for controlling the early outbreak of a pandemic.

November 26, 2020 (Medical Image Analysis)

COVID-AL: The diagnosis of COVID-19 with deep active learning

Xing Wu, Cheng Chen, Mingyu Zhong et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2020.101913>

The researchers propose a weakly-supervised deep active learning framework called COVID-AL to diagnose COVID-19 with CT scans and patient-level labels. The COVID-AL consists of the lung region segmentation with a 2D U-Net and the diagnosis of COVID-19 with a novel hybrid active learning strategy. The results show that the proposed COVID-AL outperforms the state-of-the-art active learning approaches. With only 30% of the data, the COVID-AL achieves over 95% accuracy of the deep learning method using the whole dataset.

November 26, 2020 (Toxicology and Industrial Health)

Ventilation use in nonmedical settings during COVID-19: Cleaning protocol, maintenance, and recommendations.

Nembhard, Melanie D; Burton, D Jeff; Cohen, Joel M

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0748233720967528>

In this article, the authors review the role that building ventilation can play in minimizing the risk of SARS-CoV-2 transmission in nonmedical environments (e.g. office buildings and school classrooms) and some recommended protocols to follow for its proper use, including cleaning and maintaining mechanical ventilation systems for businesses, schools and homes.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

October 23, 2020 (Rural Special Education Quarterly)

Free Appropriate Public Education in the Time of COVID-19

J. Matt Jameson, Sondra M. Stegenga, Joanna Ryan et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/8756870520959659>

US schools were closed during the pandemic, however, the delivery of educational services did not stop. This included the ongoing provision of services mandated by federal law under the Americans With Disabilities Act (ADA) and the Individuals With Disabilities Education Act (IDEA). The authors describe the potential legal implications for schools, students with disabilities, and their families with a focus on challenges faced in rural areas.

October 27, 2020 (Public Health Report)

The COVID-19 Pandemic: An Opportunity to Transform Higher Education in Public Health

Beth A. Resnick, Paulani C. Mui, Janice Bowie et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0033354920966024>

Higher education in public health faces several challenges during the pandemic. The immediacy of the pandemic forced schools and programs of public health to shift to remote learning and to support response efforts. The authors elucidate opportunities to improve public health education.

November 16, 2020 (Telematics and Informatics)

Broadband and economic growth in China: An empirical study during the COVID-19 pandemic period

Xiaoqun Zhang

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2020.101533>

Dr Zhang proposed an economic model that describes the special role of broadband in economic growth during the COVID-19 pandemic period. Empirical research was conducted using the data of China to investigate how broadband affected China's economic growth during this period. The findings showed broadband alleviated China's economic losses during the first few months of 2020 when the new coronavirus spread across the country, and broadband affected China's economic growth. These findings have policy implications for China as well as other countries.